

IMPACTS OF CORONAVIRUS PANDEMIC ON TOURISM OF CENTRAL ASIA

Ulmasova Bahora Asrorovna

MA student of Silk Road International
University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage
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1. Abstract

5 Central Asian (CA) countries (Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan) are one of the most developing states in tourism sector for attracting many tourists with its rich history and culture. During the period 2020 to 2022 tourism industry of these nations highly damaged by COVID-19 and it showed its negative impacts on Gross Domestic Products (GDP), social life, industries and other sectors of life in countries all over the world. This research takes the first step in exploring the impact of COVID-19 on tourist arrivals, tourism imports, GDP of CA countries, and it also analyzes a comparison between pre-pandemic and post Covid-19 conditions of tourism industry, and we use latest data and statistics for clarification it, as well. This study utilized only secondary data and it has been collected by previous studies and literature reviews. Several pieces of research and thesis papers, government documents used for collecting essential information for study.

Key words: GDP, tourist arrivals, tourism industry, pre-pandemic, post COVID-19 conditions, literature review.

2. Introduction

The COVID-19 brought unparalleled effects to tourism industry of the globe. Central Asia attracts many tourists with its rich history and a culture around the world as other continents in the field of business. In 2019, total number of tourist arrivals both Europe and Central Asia was around 1.2 billion. As a consequence of spreading unexpected virus around the world, all the states temporarily closed their borders, and it caused to drop total amount of GDP in the Globe, job places, tourism, hotel industries, social life and every field of life of individuals. Both domestic and international travelers cancelled their trips during Coronavirus pandemic. Many hotels and restaurants faced challenges and some of them bankrupted by the COVID-19. Due to the pandemic outbreak the total number of world tourism industry decreased by 80 % (UNWTO, 2020a). It also showed its negative effects on tourism of Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Turkmenistan, because these countries loss many job opportunities, closed their borders, both inbound and outbound tourism almost stopped temporary until the beginning of 2021.

2.1 Objectives of the research

The tourism industry is seen to be entering into a great crisis in all sectors. Central Asian countries' industries are one of the affected and almost all of the states did not make a profit by tourism from 2020 to 2022. The hotels, export and imports, airlines, companies' operations were stopped. The objectives of study are followings:

1. To analyze the impacts of pandemic on tourism industry in evidence of Central Asian countries and its place in global GDP.
2. To investigate previous studies about COVID-19.
3. To examine tourist flows before, during and after pandemic in 5 states.
4. To explore statistics based on Gross Domestic Products of Central Asia.
5. To discuss study findings, conclusions and give recommendations.

2.2 Literature review

There is different type of Literature available in a term of coronavirus's impacts on tourism. The main discussions of these studies are about socio-economic effects of pandemic in the world, how will tourism change in the near future and etc. Some articles discuss the risk perceptions of tourists and travel intentions during the period of pandemic. In this Literature review we consider that previous studies of researchers which is based on tourism and pandemic.

Risk perception is connected with the situation which is deal with consuming a tourism product service or making a travel decision (Reisinger, Mavondo, 2005). Travelers sometimes can expose to risk their health while choosing an unknown trip destination. 3 years ago, coronavirus pandemic highly damaged more than 210 countries' tourism industry, however it helped to make the safety of international travel in all over the world (Turnsek et al.,2020).

3. Data and methodology

In this part of research, we investigate data collections and used methodology of the paper. And all the collecting information deal with global tourism industry, condition of Central Asia (CA) during the period of pandemic, and also it compares pre-pandemic and post-COVID-19 conditions in evidence of 5 countries.

3.1 Data collection

Tourism sector plays a crucial role among the countries in a worldwide and total amount of travel and tourism trade contained 10 trillion US dollars in 2019 before the pandemic and it was equal to 10.4% of Global Gross Domestic

Products. However, it was 7.7 trillion US\$ in 2022 after the coronavirus and it represented 7.6% of global GDP. Central Asian countries is one of the most developing nations in the field of tourism and it is known all over the world as a part of Great Silk Road. There are 5 countries and they are Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, and Turkmenistan. All of the CA countries' tourism industry was fastest-growing sector in 2019 before the coronavirus pandemic. Central Asian nations' GDP growth was 6.6% in 2019, which was dropped to 2,9% in 2020. According to the Eurasian Development Bank total number of GDP in Central Asia was \$291 Billion in 2020. The most developed country among the CA counties is Kazakhstan. Unexpected virus showed it negative impacts in a worldwide. Before the pandemic, in 2019, 1.2 billion international tourist arrivals visited in Central Asia and Europe.

Country	GDP (\$ billion)	% of tourism in GDP	% employment in tourism	% tourism in exports	International tourist arrivals, in mln	UNESCO World Heritage Sites listed
Kazakhstan	181.6	5.2	4.9	4.1	8.6	5
Uzbekistan	57.9	4.5	4.6	21.1	6.7	5
Tajikistan	8.1	6.4	6.6	28.4	1.3	2
Kyrgyzstan	8.4	8.3	8.5	18.6	4.0	2
Turkmenistan	40.7	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	3

Source: Helbe, Fink (2020); UNWTO (2020a); UNWTO (2020b); WTTC (2020).

In this table, indicators compared among the countries in 2019. The country which is more tourist visited is Kazakhstan with 8.6 million. And Uzbekistan welcomed 6,748,500 international tourists at the same year. There is no data available on government websites about GDP, tourist arrivals and employment rate of Turkmenistan. A year before pandemic, Tajikistan showed the best result on tourism exports with 28.4% among 5 nations. And other states such as, Kazakhstan 4,1%, Uzbekistan 21.1% and Kyrgyzstan 18.6% performed in tourism exports. The higher employment in the field of tourism rate was in Kyrgyzstan and it was equal to 8.5%. In the second place was Tajikistan with 6.6% employment rate, while Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan faced some challenges.

In this following data, we investigate how pandemic effects on tourist flow of CA nations.

*Uzbekistan: Kyrgyzstan: Kazakhstan: Tajikistan:
Turkmenistan:*

2018 – 5,346,200;	7 million	8.79 million	1,035,000	N/A
2019 – 6,748,500;	8,508,000	8,515,000	1,257,300	N/A
2020 – 1,420,300;	69 thousand	2,035,000	350,000	N/A
2022 – 5,200,000;	1,970,900	3.4 million	431,000	N/A

Uzbekistan welcomed 6.5 million visitors in 2019, and it was dropped by 1,5 million in 2020. 8,515,000 travelers visited in Kazakhstan in 2019, and 2,035,000 tourists came during the pandemic period. At the same time, in Kyrgyzstan tourist arrivals represented as 8.5 million, however this statistic changed into 69000 tourists flow in 2020. Tajikistan is also welcomed approximately 1.3 million visitors before pandemic and 350,000 people visited in 2020. During the period of coronavirus pandemic many hotels, companies, and industries paused their job, due to it they loss many job places and some of them faced to bankrupt, as well. In addition to it, 6.2% of total GDP of Kazakhstan is belong to tourism sector. And it is equal to 5% of GDP in Kyrgyzstan, 3.4% of GDP in Uzbekistan, and 1% of GDP in Tajikistan. It is necessary to highlight that, these countries tourism sector was at a high level before pandemic, due to the many cancellation and closing of borders they came across many challenges during pandemic, however governments try to recover step by step after COVID-19.

3.2 Methodology

In this review we used only secondary data for describing some differences and gather literature reviews. For collecting data, we used some websites such as Google scholar, Research Gate, journal articles, previous studies which done by scholars, and reports taken from UNWTO ,2020; the World Bank and others for analyzing negative impacts of COVID-19 on 5 nation's travel sectors.

4. Result/Key Findings

COVID-19 effected to the Global tourism unreliable level. Total GDP of Global industry was dropped sharply. Due to the pandemic in Kazakhstan unemployment rate increased from 0.2% to 5%. Tajikistan's GDP dropped to 1.6% in during 2020. Besides that, there is no any data and reports about impacts of COVID-19 on tourism industry of Turkmenistan, but government should attract more tourists for country's development. In 2020, during the 8 months Uzbekistan's unemployment rate increased from 9.4% to almost 15%. If all countries attract more tourists nowadays, they can make a more profit form this business, and it tends to development.

5. Conclusion/Policy implications

In conclusion, around the central Asian countries both inbound and outbound tourism types stopped for the moment. This study gives more detailed information about how tourism was in the period of coronavirus pandemic and it helps to focus on to increase tourists number in all countries. Besides that,

government should inspect risk perceptions of tourists during difficult situations and they have to focus on tourists' health, as well. The second recommendation for Central Asian countries is to attract many tourists, and develop both domestic and international tourism at a level of perfection.

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